

Site Suitability Analysis of Solid Waste Disposal in Aba South L.G.A, Abia State, Nigeria Using Geospatial Technology

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ABSTRACT - Solid waste disposal is an important part of waste management system, which requires much attention to avoid environmental pollution and health problems. This study was aimed at carrying out site suitability for solid wastes disposal in Aba South LGA using geospatial techniques with the specific objectives of: identifying the spatial distribution of solid waste bin points in Aba South LGA, investigating the existing methods of solid wastes disposal and performing suitability analysis of solid wastes using the United Nations Environmental Protection (UNEP) 2005 guidelines. To achieve this, the field surveys were carried out to obtain the coordinate points of waste bins in the study area using the Extrex 10 Handheld GPS receiver. Geospatial techniques were used in carrying out site suitability analysis to determine and propose suitable sites for solid waste dumping. The ArcGIS 10.2 was used to carryout suitability analysis using buffer and overlay analysis. Results showed that there about thirty five (35) waste bins distributed within the commercials areas in Aba South LGA. These waste bins are concentrated around Enugu-Port-Harcourt Road and Port-Harcourt Roads. Enugu-Port-Harcourt has about six (6) waste bins while Port-Harcourt has two and Azikiwe Road have three (3) and two (2) waste bins respectively. From the overlay and multi-criteria analysis, a total of four (4) suitable sites were identified in Aba South LGA. Two suitable sites were found along Enugu-Port Harcourt Expressway with an area of 6.234 and 2.757 Hectares respectively while along Asa-Nnentu Road two (2) suites were equally identified with an area of 6.325 and 1.440 Hectares respectively. This brings to the suitable sites to a total area of 16.756 hectares and a 0.14% of the total landmass of Aba South LGA. This study recommends that: Solid waste bin should be well distributed with Aba South LGA to reduce the menace of improper waste disposal along major roads and streets in the city, the Abia State Environmental Protection Agency (ASEPA) should ensure timely and regular disposal of solid wastes from waste bin collection points and there should be regular sensitization by the relevant bodies on the environmental and health implications of improper solid waste disposal.

1. Introduction

Solid waste is a global environmental problem in today's world both in less developing and developed countries. Increasing population, rapid economic growth and the rise in community living standards accelerate solid waste generation in the world (Elmira *et al.*, 2010).

Solid waste disposal is an important part of waste management system, which requires much attention to avoid environmental pollution and health problems. However, most solid waste disposal sites are found on the outskirts of the urban areas close to water bodies, farmlands, settlements, roads and in most cases blocking drainages and streets. These are suitable sites for the incubation and proliferation of flies, mosquitoes and rodents. They transfer diseases that affect human health (Abul, 2010).

In recent years, there has been an increase in the volume of waste generated across the nation, due to number of factors which include; high population growth rate increasing urbanization and increase per capital income (Taye, 2014). Inappropriate disposal of solid waste can be manifested by contamination of surface and ground water, soil contamination through direct waste contact, air pollution by burning of wastes,

spreading of diseases by different vectors like birds, insects and rodents or uncontrolled release of methane by anaerobic decomposition of waste.

Rapid increase in population results in increase in rising quantity of solid waste with higher rate and this remains a challenge for developing cities which Aba South is inclusive. The rate of exploitation, production and consumption are population dependent which invariably determine the rate of production of environmental externalities in the form of obnoxious substances which pollute the environment – the air, water and land (Uwadiogwu and Iyi, 2015). This waste is ultimately thrown into municipal disposal sites and due to poor and ineffective management, the dumpsites turn to sources of environmental and health hazards to people living in the vicinity of such dumps. One of the main aspects of concern is the pollution caused to the earth; be it land, air and water (Ndukwe et al, 2019)

In Aba South LGA, facilities for house to house collection of solid waste are absent as solid wastes are deposited at designated waste bin collection points, from where vehicles can collect them for final disposal to solid waste dump sites. These waste bin points are generally at open spaces along street ends which usually becomes nuisance points to urban dwellers (Abdullah, 2013). However, these solid wastes are not regularly collected from the waste bin points for disposal and they therefore decompose and create an unhealthy odours because they are sometimes left without collection for months, provide breeding places for flies, ants, scorpions, snakes, and then papers and other light object are blown around by wind. Most of the refuse end up in the drains and thereby contribute to the pollution of rivers and drainages.

Studies have shown that most of the solid waste disposal sites in Nigeria are pits which are made by construction companies or are created by erosion (Ismail, *et al.*, 2016). There are little or no precaution to protect both natural and human environment from the pollution caused by these decomposed solid waste in our environment. The lack of organize and effective solid waste disposal in our cities in Nigeria can be attributed to the lack of substantial National Waste Management Plan and lack of funds for environmental agencies to execute their activities (Ismail, *et al.*, 2016).

Therefore, there is need to adopt techniques that will be cost effective and that will reduce the time for solid waste disposal. The technology that will help in appropriate planning by analyzing the waste situation of the area and determining the suitable sites for waste disposal. This is where geospatial technologies plays a huge role as they are planning and decision support tools and when integrated into solid waste disposal, it ensures proper solid waste disposal in Aba South LGA.

In waste disposal planning, a geographic information system plays an important role. GIS is used in waste disposal for a variety of reasons, including decision support for locating suitable landfills and temporal monitoring of disposal locations, including landfills. Due to the competing criteria, solid waste landfill siting is a complex and time-consuming operation in the traditional method of SWM. Furthermore, the primary purpose of the landfill site selection procedure is to ensure that the disposal facility is located in the best possible area, with the least amount of detrimental influence on the environment and population. Using geospatial techniques ensures a thorough review process to determine the best possible disposal place that complies with government standards while also minimizing costs (Elsai, Kefelegn and Dechasa, 2022).

This study used ArcGIS software package to carry out the suitability analysis of solid wastes disposal points using GIS multi-criteria analysis method. The buffer and overlay analysis was used as well as GIS multi-criteria analysis.

Municipal solid waste is one of the problems facing many cities all over the world especially in developing countries that are faced with problems of unplanned urban growth, rapid urbanization and low economy.

In Aba South LGA, solid waste are generally located at open spaces along streets which becomes nuisance to urban dwellers as these solid wastes are not regularly collected by the authority for disposal and they therefore decompose and create an unhealthy environment.

The Abia State Environmental Protection Agency (ASEPA) which are in charge of solid waste disposal and management have done a great work in this regard, however, there is no timely evacuation of the solid wastes to the dump sites and also there is indiscriminate sitting of waste bin points in the city without considerations to its site suitability.

Therefore, this research seeks ways of using geospatial technology in determining suitable sites for solid waste collection and disposal in the study area.

The aim of this study is to carry out site suitability for solid wastes disposal in Aba South LGA using geospatial techniques.

The following are the specific objectives of the study:

1. To identify the spatial distribution of solid waste bin points.
2. To investigate the existing methods of solid wastes disposal.
3. To carryout suitability analysis of solid wastes using the United Nations Environmental Protection (UNEP) 2005 guidelines.

2. Materials and Method

2.1 The Study Area

Aba South LGA is the main city centre of Abia State, south-east Nigeria. It is located on the Aba River. Aba is made up of many villages such as; Aba-Ukwu, Eziukwu-Aba, Obuda-Aba, Umuokpoji-Aba and other villages from Ohazu merged due to administrative convenience. Aba was established by the Ngwa clan of Igbo people of Nigeria as a market town and then later a military post was placed there by the British colonial administration in 1901. The city became a collecting point for agricultural products following the British made railway running through it to Port Harcourt. Aba is a major urban settlement and commercial centre in a region that is surrounded by small villages and towns. The indigenous people of Aba are the Ngwa. Aba is well known for its craftsmen.

Figure 1: Map of the Study Area

2.2. Methodology

a. Data Requirement

The different datasets are required for this study and they include:

- i. Waste bin collection coordinate points datasets
- ii. Waste disposal coordinate datasets
- iii. High resolution ortho-rectified ALOS PARSER DEM
- iv. Open Street Map Datasets
- v. Administrative map of Aba South Local Government Area

b. Data Acquisition

Acquisition of Primary Datasets

The primary datasets was acquired from field visits to the study area. The primary datasets acquired include: The coordinates of waste bin/collection points, attribute data (non-spatial data) that describes the waste collection points and other features and the coordinate points of features such as schools, markets and religious centers in the study area.

Waste Bin/ Collection Points

The Extrex 10 handheld GPS receiver was used to obtain the coordinate points of the waste bin in the study area. The corresponding data were also obtained.

Acquisition of Secondary Datasets

The secondary datasets were obtained from already existing data from other sources. The secondary datasets used include:

- i. The administrative map Aba South Local Government Area: The shapefile of Abia State containing the seventeen (17) local government area of the state were obtained from the Office of Surveyor General of Abia State. The shapefile was imported into the ArcGIS environment and using the clipping tool, the shapefile of Aba South Local Government Area was clipped out.
- ii. High resolution ortho-rectified ALOS PARSER DEM (12.5m) acquired from www.asf.alaska.edu website.
- iii. The road network and water body datasets was obtained from Open Street map datasets acquired from Open Street Map platform.

3. Result And Discussion

Spatial Distribution of Waste Bins in Aba South LGA

The waste bin coordinate points obtained using the Extrex 10 Hand-held GPS receiver through field survey was prepared in excel workspace and they were plotted in ArcGIS environment to show the spatial distribution of waste bins.

Fig 6.0 shows the spatial distribution of waste bin.

Figure 2: Spatial Distribution of Waste Bins.

From the results in Fig. 2.1, it was observed that there about thirty-five (35) waste bins distributed in Aba South LGA. These waste bins are not evenly distributed as they are observed to be concentrated around Enugu-Port-Harcourt Road and Port-Harcourt Roads. Enugu-Port-Harcourt has about six (6) waste bins while Port-Harcourt has two and Azikiwe Road have three (3) and two (2) waste bins respectively. It was further observed that there are not enough waste bins available in Aba South LGA as the waste bins are concentrated within market and commercials areas.

Existing methods of solid waste disposal

The existing methods were selected for the overlay and buffer analysis. These methods are needed to process the GIS multi-criteria analysis for the study.

Hydrology

In carrying out this analysis, longer distances from river and streams banks were given more preferences for suitable solid waste dumping sites. In Aba South LGA, the major and important river is the Waterside River. Therefore, to maintain the environmental health of this river, a minimum of 300m Euclidean distance was adopted for the study to avoid all forms of water pollution. Landfill/disposal site close to surface water body lead to “effects on water quality, quantity and aquatic habitat loss, disturbance or alteration. Surface water body is a natural resource that is very vital to humans and other animals on earths. Therefore, to avoid pollution of water surfaces, landfill/disposal site must not be in an area where it can affect or pollute water surfaces.

Fig. 6.1 shows the buffer distance for the hydrology

Figure. 3: Hydrology criteria map.

From the result of the analysis in Figure 3, it will be observed that only one river is found in the study area which is Waterside River. Waste disposal site is not to be located within the buffer zone of the river which was marked blue on the map.

Elevation/ Slope

Elevation is an important parameter in the identification of suitable sites for solid waste landfill site. Different research shows that areas with high slopes will have high risk of pollution and potentially not a good site for dumping. This study therefore considers areas with lower slope highly suitable than the areas with higher slope. The elevation data were obtained from the high resolution Alos Parser DEM for the study area. The DEM was used to generate the slope for ABA South LGA in ArcMap 10.2 environment. Figure 4 shows the slope map.

Figure 4: Elevation (Slope) criteria map.

From the results in Fig. 4, it was observed that the slope range of the study area is from 0.0002 to 14.7334. Flat surfaces are more suitable for landfill site than areas that are on a steep. The majority of the study area falls under the slope class of 0-10%, which covers 99.4% of the total study area. It therefore shows that most of the land in the study area is suitable for waste disposal under this criteria.

According to Sener *et al.* (2011) and Leao (2001), the land area with a slope less than 10% is highly suitable for solid waste dumping. This shows that slope is not a significant criterion for solid waste dumping site selection in the study area.

Major Roads

As the general concept, the landfills shall not be located within 100m of any major highways, city streets or other transportation routes. Solid waste dumping site must be located at suitable distance from roads network in order to facilitate transportation and consequently to reduce relative costs. For this study, a buffer of 200m distance from main roads was adopted.

Fig. 6.3 shows the buffer map of the major roads.

Figure 5. Buffer map of Major Roads.

From the results of the analysis in Fig.5, it was observed that about 13 major roads were identified within the study area, and these major roads include PH-Enugu Highway, Port Harcourt Road, Azikiwe Road, Cemetery Road, Ibadan and Ohanku Road etc. Solid waste disposal site is not to be sited within the buffer zones of these major roads.

Restricted Areas

The areas categorized as the protected areas in this study includes churches, mosques, schools, parks and others. The landfill should not be located in close proximity to these sensitive areas listed above to limit of 500m buffer surrounding. The increase in distance increases the suitability.

Fig. 5 shows the buffer map of the restricted areas.

Figure 6. Buffer map of Restricted Areas.

Overlaying and Identifying Suitable Sites

The site selection for solid waste disposal dumping site involves comparison of different criteria based on environmental, social and economic impact. Therefore, based on experience and likely impact on surrounding environment, different weights were assigned to all the parameters. The larger the weight, the more significant is the criterion in the overall utility. The weights were developed by providing a series of pair wise comparisons of the relative importance of factors to the suitability of pixels for the activity being evaluated. The procedure by which the weights were produced follows the logic developed by Saaty (1980) under the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP). Weight rates were given based on pair wise comparison of factors.

The factors and their resulting weights were used as input for the Multi Criteria Evaluation (MCE) module for weighted linear combination of overlay analysis. In order to combine all the layers to process overlay analysis, standardization of each data set to a common scale of 1, 2, 3, 4 (value 1 = unsuitable (restricted), value 2 = less suitable, value 3 = moderately suitable, value 4 = highly suitable) was performed. Finally, all the parameters were weighted with their respective percent of influence and overlay to produce the suitability map.

Fig. 7. Overlay Analysis to determine Suitable Sites.

Suitable Sites for Solid Waste Disposal

From the overlay and multi-criteria analysis in consideration of their degree of importance were considered in selecting suitable solid waste dumping site.

After the overlay analysis of the given factors the following suitable solid waste dumping site map was produced and the most suitable area for solid waste dumping site is shaded green color as shown in the suitability map.

Fig. 8. Suitability Map showing Suitable Sites for Solid Waste Disposal.

From the results in Fig 8, it was observed that there are four suitable sites for solid waste disposal in Aba South LGA. These sites are found within the southern part of Aba South LGA. Two suitable sites were found along Enugu-Port Harcourt Expressway with an area of 6.234 and 2.757 Hectares respectively while along Asa-Nnentu Road two (2) sites were equally identified with an area of 6.325 and 1.440 Hectares respectively.

Therefore, a total of 16.756 hectares were identified to be suitable sites for solid waste disposal in Aba South LGA. This amount to 0.14% of the total landmass of Aba South LGA.

Table 1 shows the area and location of the suitable sites for solid waste disposal in Aba South LGA.

Table 1: The Area and Location of the Suitable Sites for Solid Waste Disposal.

S/N	Name	Location	Area (Ha)
1	SS01	Enugu-Port Harcourt Expressway	6.234
2	SS02	Enugu-Port Harcourt Expressway	2.757
3	SS03	Asa-Nnentu Road	6.325
4	SS04	Asa-Nnentu Road	1.440

4. Conclusion

This study has shown the capabilities of integrating Remote Sensing (RS) and GIS multi-criteria methods in analyzing and identifying suitable sites for solid waste disposal. This study achieved its specific objectives by successfully analyzing and identifying suitable sites for solid disposal in Aba South LGA, based on the United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP) 2005 criteria for solid waste disposal.

The selected suitable sites are easy to access and managed for disposal of solid wastes in Aba South LGA. These suitable sites are far away from any water sources and other variables put into analysis. Hence, the capacity to use GIS and remote sensing technology for the effective identification of suitable solid waste dumping site will minimize the environmental risk and human health problems

5. Recommendation

From the results of the study, the following are recommended:

1. Solid waste bin should be well distributed with Aba South LGA to reduce the menace of improper waste disposal along major roads and streets in the city.
2. The Abia State Environmental Protection Agency (ASEPA) should ensure timely and regular disposal of solid wastes from waste bin collection points.
3. There should be regular sensitization by the relevant bodies on the environmental and health implications of improper solid waste disposal.
4. The results from this study should be by relevant bodies and agencies in making an informed decision in environmental protection and waste disposal.

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